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САЛЬМОНЕЛЬОЗ У СУЧАСНІЙ КЛІНІЧНІЙ ПРАКТИЦІ: ОГЛЯД ЛІТЕРАТУРИ

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SALMONELLOSIS IN CONTEMPORARY CLINICAL PRACTICE: A LITERATURE REVIEW

Анотація:

Сальмонельоз зберігає значення однієї з провідних бактеріальних кишкових інфекцій, актуальність якої посилюється циркуляцією нетифоїдних сероварів, ризиком інвазивних форм у вразливих груп населення та зростанням антибіотикорезистентності.

Мета роботи - узагальнити сучасні літературні дані 2023-2025 рр. щодо епідеміологічних тенденцій, клінічних проявів, факторів ризику тяжкого перебігу, діагностики, лікувальної тактики, проблеми антибіотикорезистентності та профілактики сальмонельозу.

Abstract:

Salmonellosis remains one of the leading bacterial intestinal infections and continues to be clinically relevant because of the circulation of non-typhoidal serovars, the risk of invasive disease in vulnerable groups, and increasing antimicrobial resistance. The analysis showed that modern clinical practice should rely on a risk-oriented approach: most cases present as self-limited gastroenteritis, whereas infants, young children, older adults, and immunocompromised patients are at higher risk of dehydration, bacteremia, and septic complications. Appropriate management requires bacteriological confirmation, assessment of serovar distribution and antimicrobial susceptibility, early identification of severe disease, and justified use of antibacterial therapy. Salmonellosis should therefore be regarded not merely as a foodborne infection, but as a multifactorial clinical and public health challenge that requires vigilance, laboratory support, antimicrobial stewardship, and prevention within a One Health framework.

The purpose of the work is to summarize the current literature data of 2023-2025 regarding epidemiological trends, clinical manifestations, risk factors for a severe course, diagnosis, treatment tactics, the problem of antibiotic resistance and prevention of salmonellosis.

Ключові слова: сальмонельоз, нетифоїдні сальмонели, антибіотикорезистентність, діти, гастроентерит, клінічна практика.

Keywords: salmonellosis, non-typhoidal Salmonella, antimicrobial resistance, children, gastroenteritis, clinical practice.

Матеріали та методи. Проведено огляд сучасних відкритих наукових джерел 2023-2025 рр., що висвітлюють клінічні, епідеміологічні та профілактичні аспекти сальмонельозу. До аналізу включено статті й огляди, доступні у відкритому доступі, з перевагою українським публікаціям та роботам авторів Буковинського державного медичного університету.

Materials and methods. A review of modern open scientific sources for 2023-2025 covering clinical, epidemiological and preventive aspects of salmonellosis was conducted. Articles and reviews available in the

public domain are included in the analysis, with preference given to Ukrainian publications and works by the authors of the Bukovinian State Medical University.

Introduction. Salmonellosis remains one of the most important acute bacterial intestinal infections, which has not only infectological, but also significant public and sanitary significance. In modern reviews, it is considered as a leading zoonotic food pathogen capable of causing relatively mild self-limited gastroenteritis, but under certain conditions - invasive forms with bacteremia and sepsis. S. Enteritidis and S. Typhimurium remain the main serovars of epidemic importance, and infection control is increasingly linked

to a One Health approach that integrates clinical, veterinary and nutritional aspects of prevention [2].

The main part. Summarizing the current literature shows that the clinical significance of salmonellosis is determined by a combination of three circumstances: the wide circulation of the pathogen in the food chain, the high frequency of nontyphoid serovars, and the ability of the infection to take a severe course in vulnerable patients. According to modern reviews, *Salmonella* has more than 2,500 serovars, is transmitted mainly through contaminated products of animal origin, water or contact with animals, and the clinical manifestations and consequences of infection depend on the serovar and the state of the macroorganism. Primary symptoms most often include diarrhea, abdominal pain, fever, nausea, and vomiting; in the typical course, they last from several days to one week, however, in young children and people with reduced immunity, progression to systemic lesions is possible [2, 3].

For Ukraine, the problem remains of practical relevance. In the domestic study of the epidemic process, it was established that salmonellosis was registered at a fairly high level in the Zaporizhzhia region in 2018-2022, and intensive morbidity rates among children exceeded similar rates among adults by 4-7 times; an additional threat was the circulation of strains resistant to cephalosporins, ampicillin and fluoroquinolones. Newer clinical observations by the authors of BSMU

also emphasize pediatric vulnerability: in 2024, the incidence of salmonellosis among children in Ukraine increased by 6%, and children accounted for 40% of all cases of intestinal infections [1,6].

Risk groups need special attention. In modern foreign sources, they include children under 5 years of age, the elderly, and immunocompromised patients; it is in these categories that dehydration, bacteremia, meningitis and other serious complications occur more often. In 2025, it was emphasized that non-typhoidal *Salmonella* ceased to be perceived only as a cause of "ordinary food poisoning": the increasing frequency of cases among vulnerable contingents and the risk of fatal consequences in conditions of limited access to medical care make the infection an important clinical problem [3, 5].

Pediatric features of the course are of direct importance to the doctor. According to the BSMU, under modern conditions, 70% of cases of hospitalized salmonellosis in children were caused by *S. Enteritidis*, while *S. Typhimurium* was more often isolated in the younger age group. In children over 3 years of age, severe abdominal pain, repeated vomiting, and a severe condition at the time of hospitalization were more likely to be noted, and in younger children, longer vomiting, which made it difficult to carry out oral rehydration. Such differences indicate the need for a differentiated clinical assessment already at the initial stage of providing care [6].

Table 1

Clinical guidelines for managing a patient with salmonellosis in modern practice

Clinical aspect	Modern data	Practical significance
Leading causative agents	Non-typhoid serovars <i>S. Enteritidis</i> and <i>S. Typhimurium</i> have the greatest clinical significance; in children, their distribution may differ by age.	The probable serovar should be taken into account when assessing the risk of a severe course.
Typical course	Gastroenteritis with diarrhea, fever, nausea, vomiting and abdominal pain lasting 2-7 days is most often observed.	Most cases require careful assessment of the degree of dehydration and dynamic monitoring.
Risk groups	Young children, the elderly and immunocompromised patients are the most vulnerable.	In these patients, invasive forms and complications should be ruled out earlier.
Diagnosis	Bacteriological confirmation remains basic; serotyping and molecular methods are important for epidemic surveillance.	Laboratory verification helps clarify the etiology and the choice of antibacterial tactics.
Antibiotic resistance	Resistance is associated with efflux pumps, enzymatic inactivation, target switching, biofilms and plasmid mechanisms.	Empiric therapy should be combined with assessment of local sensitivity profiles.

Note. Compiled according to data [2, 3, 4, 6].

In terms of diagnostics, modern practice requires a combination of clinical analysis with timely bacteriological verification. The selection of *Salmonella* spp. from clinical material remains the basic criterion for case confirmation, and serotyping and molecular methods, in particular PFGE, MLVA and WGS, play an increasingly important role in outbreaks and tracing the source of infection. This approach allows not only to confirm the diagnosis, but also to specify the epidemiological origin of the case, which is especially important in the conditions of an outbreak [2, 6].

Antibiotic resistance is a separate challenge of modern clinical practice. According to modern reviews, for severe or complicated forms, antibacterial therapy is used, taking into account the risk group and the clinical situation; at the same time, due to the spread of resistance to fluoroquinolones, the role of ceftriaxone and azithromycin as empiric options is increasingly being discussed. At the same time, the pathogen has formed a complex of defense mechanisms: enzymatic inactivation of drugs, active removal of antibiotics from the cell, modification of targets, reduction of the permeability of the outer membrane, biofilm formation, and

plasmid-mediated transfer of resistance. Therefore, the decision regarding antibacterial therapy cannot be templated and should be based on the assessment of the severity of the course, the patient's age, the presence of immunodeficiency and local data on sensitivity [3, 4].

Results and discussion. The conducted review allows us to formulate several practically significant conclusions. First, salmonellosis in the modern clinic should be considered as an infection with a highly variable course: from short-term gastroenteritis to invasive and septic forms. Secondly, for Ukraine, the pediatric component is of particular importance, since children form the most vulnerable contingent both in terms of morbidity and severe course. Third, epidemiological monitoring and clinical tactics are increasingly closely related to the problem of antibiotic resistance, which forces a shift from empiric standard treatment to a more personalized approach. Finally, the effective control of salmonellosis goes beyond only the clinical management of the patient, as it includes food safety, sanitary control, intersectoral supervision and educational work with the population [1, 2, 5].

Thus, modern clinical practice regarding salmonellosis should be based on early identification of patients at risk of a severe course, verification of the diagnosis by laboratory methods, sound antimicrobial tactics and preventive measures within the One Health concept. This model makes it possible to simultaneously reduce clinical risks for the patient and prevent the spread of resistant strains in the population [2, 4, 5].

Conclusions. 1. Salmonellosis remains an actual bacterial intestinal infection with the predominance of non-typhoid serovars *S. Enteritidis* and *S. Typhimurium* and a significant role of the food route of transmission.

2. Young children, the elderly, and immunocompromised patients are the most vulnerable to a severe course, in whom dehydration, bacteremia, and septic complications occur more often.

3. For modern clinical practice, bacteriological verification of the diagnosis, assessment of serovar and antibiotic sensitivity, as well as early detection of signs of an invasive course are key.

4. Increasing antibiotic resistance of *Salmonella* requires a careful and individualized approach to antibacterial therapy.

5. Effective containment of salmonellosis is possible only with a combination of clinical vigilance, epidemiological surveillance, food safety and prevention in the One Health format.

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